

SURVEILLANCE CARD RIFT VALLEY FEVER (RVF) - Bulk milk surveillance in ruminants in high-risk areas and season

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Bulk milk serology and antigen testing for Rift Valley Fever Virus in a risk-based sample of dairy cattle, sheep and goat farms (areas of increased risk of virus introduction and high-risk season summer and autumn).
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen.
3	Target species and group	Cattle, sheep and goats, healthy animals.
4	Target sector / production type	Milk production.
5	Geographical area covered	Area of increased risk of virus introduction. According to a recent EFSA opinion, surveillance should target countries in Southern Europe which are close to endemic areas, as well as regions around large airports and ports, where introduction of infected mosquitoes seems likely (1).
6	Age group	Adult, lactating females.
7	Sampling point and strategy	On farm or at milk collection sites, selective sampling of farms in high-risk areas.
8	Sampling time period	Focus on high-risk period (summer and autumn) recommended. Monthly samples are recommended during this period.
9	Sampling matrix	Milk, pooled sample of all lactating animals of a herd.
10	Type of disease indicators	Virus detection, combined with detection of antibodies.
11	Sampling unit	Herd.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of high-risk areas - Random selection of milk producing farms within high-risk areas (alternatively, volunteering sentinel farms could be used) Monthly testing of a bulk milk sample during the high-risk period.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Testing of samples with RT-PCR for RVFV and VNT for antibodies to RVFV.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Only applicable if the sampling protocol ensures a representative sample (see 16)
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined and reported. Ideally 95 %.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	This activity targets a known population and the sensitivity of detection can be calculated if the sampling protocol ensures a representative sample, which can be achieved by different sampling strategies, including for instance random, stratified, or risk-based. Estimation of the sensitivity in the latter case depends on proper definition of the risk strata and their relative risks. The component is expected to have high sensitivity.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Q-Fever, Brucellosis, Tick-borne encephalitis.
18	References	1) EFSA AHAW Panel (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare), Nielsen SS, Alvarez J, Bicout DJ, Calistri P, Depner K, Drewe JA, Garin-Bastuji B, Gonzales Rojas JL, GortazarSchmidt C, Herskin M, Michel V, Miranda Chueca MA, Pasquali P, Roberts HC, Sihvonen LH, Stahl K, Calvo AV, Viltrop A, Winckler C, Gubbins S, Antoniou S-E, Broglia A, Abrahantes JC, Dhollander S and Van der Stede Y, 2020. Scientific Opinion on Rift Valley Fever—assessment of effectiveness of surveillance and control measures in the EU. EFSA Journal 2020;18(11):6292, 75 pp. https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6292
19	Additional comments	A design prevalence of 0.3% could be targeted for serosurveillance in high-risk areas. (1)